

1 Under the mantra: ‘Make use of colorblind
2 friendly graphs’

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29 **Abstract**

30 Colorblindness is a genetic condition that affects a person’s ability
31 to accurately perceive colors. Several papers still exist making use
32 of rainbow colors palette to show output. In such cases, for color-
33 blind people such graphs are meaningless. In this paper we propose

34 good practices and coding solutions developed in the R Free and Open
35 Source Software to (i) simulate colorblindness, (ii) develop colorblind
36 friendly color palettes and (iii) provide the tools for converting a non-
37 colorblind friendly graph into a new image with improved colors.

38 *Keywords:* colors, colorblindness, R software, science dissemination, sci-
39 entific graphs

40 *Abbreviations:* FOSS: Free and Open Source Software

41 'I'll try out the pencils sharpened to the point of infinity which always
42 sees ahead' (Frida Kahlo¹)

43 1 A gentle introduction to colorblindness

44 Colors are related to the reflectance of light in different wavelengths of the
45 electromagnetic spectrum. However, they are not innate; we are used to give
46 names to colors based on external imprinting. With colorblindness we refer
47 to the inability to see some of the windows of the electromagnetic spectrum.

48 Colorblindness is a mostly genetic condition that affects a person's abil-
49 ity to accurately perceive colors. The main issue arises from the reduced or
50 altered functioning of the cone photoreceptors in the retina, which are re-
51 sponsible for color perception. These cones are categorized into three types:
52 L (long), M (medium), and S (short), which correspond to the colors red,
53 green, and blue, respectively (Deeb, 2005). In individuals with colorblind-
54 ness, there may be a deficiency or abnormality in one or more of these cone
55 types, resulting in difficulties in distinguishing colors (Neitz & Neitz, 2000).
56 The severity of this color perception abnormality can range from a mild dif-
57 ficulty in discerning shades to a complete inability to perceive colors (Viénot
58 et al. , 1995; Gordon, 1998; Gegenfurter et al., 2003).

59 Colorblindness is typically inherited and is more common in men than
60 in women (Simunovic, 2010). This is because the gene responsible for color-
61 blindness is linked to the X chromosome. Women have two X chromosomes
62 and therefore need two copies of the altered gene to exhibit colorblindness,
63 whereas men, with only one X chromosome, require just one copy (Birch,
64 2012).

65 The most common types of colorblindness are related to the inability
66 to detect differences between red and green: in *protanopia* people cannot
67 perceive electromagnetic radiation at 560 nm (red) while in *deutanopia* a
68 higher frequency (530 nm, green) cannot be recognized. Beside these major
69 severe types of colorblindness, *tritanopia* hampers people to distinguish a
70 very high frequency radiation type at 420 nm (blue). The inability to re-
71 cognize specific color palettes, particularly those with gradients from blue to
72 green or yellow to red, can greatly impact the perception of maps and other
73 visual materials for colorblind individuals. For example, the use of rainbow
74 color palettes in various contexts can pose challenges for those with color-
75 blindness (Crameri et al., 2020). The problem with rainbow color palettes is

¹From the English re-edition of the diary of Frida Kahlo: Kahlo, F., Lowe, S.M.,
Fuentes, C. (2005). *The Diary of Frida Kahlo: An Intimate Self-portrait*. Publisher:
Harry N. Abrams Inc, New York (USA).

76 exacerbated by the fact that they often feature smooth transitions between
77 colors that are particularly difficult to distinguish by colorblind individuals,
78 such as green and red. This can lead to misinterpretation of visual informa-
79 tion, as shades that appear distinct to someone with normal color perception
80 may appear indistinguishable or very similar to a colorblind person (Silva et
81 al., 2011).

82 In most cases, under normal human vision, we are used to distinguish col-
83 ors in a straightforward way. For instance, a person can distinguish blue from
84 yellow. However, this is dependent on the distance of colors (wavelengths)
85 in the electromagnetic spectrum. In other words, while the discrimination
86 between blue and yellow would be simple, that between very light green and
87 light yellow would not be immediate. Now, imagine what would happen if
88 this issue might include the discrimination between green and red. In most
89 of the color deficiency problems, this is the case.

90 The accessibility to scientific graphs is a crucial issue in science. The use
91 of colors that are indistinguishable to those with colorblindness still persists
92 in scientific graphs and maps, particularly when representing continuous vari-
93 ables or contrasting factors. The aim of this paper is to provide a showcase of
94 solutions developed in the R Free and Open Source Software (hereafter also
95 referred to as FOSS). We will focus on (i) colorblindness simulation, (ii) color-
96 blind friendly color palettes and (iii) the tools for converting a non-colorblind
97 friendly graph into a new image with improved colors.

98 **2 Accessibility to scientific graphs**

99 A certain amount of limitations can be associated with scientific graphs (Bur-
100 rough et al., 2015), since they imply an abstraction of reality (Palmer et al.,
101 2008). This is necessary to simplify the data and improve comprehension, but
102 it can also introduce potential ambiguities and misunderstandings, e.g., color
103 interpretation can be highly subjective. Different individuals, influenced by
104 their color perception, may draw divergent conclusions when examining the
105 same graph (Popelka et al., 2012). A simple example is provided in Fig-
106 ure 1 in which different color palettes enhance different aspects of the same
107 variable.

108 When plotting scientific graphs, in most cases green and red are con-
109 founding colors for colorblind people (Figure 2). This is a well known, but
110 often unconsidered, problem.

111 In several cases, rainbow color palettes are still being used to represent
112 the variability of patterns in space, with, generally, the blue/green color
113 representing minima and the red color representing maxima (Figure 2).

Figure 1: NDVI of Eastern Alps in Italy. The perception of spatial differences in a variable can be influenced by the choice of color palette.

Figure 2: The Amazon forest between Boa Vista and Caracaraí (Brazil), band 8 of a Sentinel-2 image (near infrared) plotted with a rainbow color palette (left). A simulation of the vision with protanopia or deuteranopia is provided on the right image. It shows the blurring effect that can occur with colorblindness.

114 Many researchers use rainbow color palettes to represent ecological pat-
115 terns or processes. Several examples exist in the literature that use such
116 a color scheme, related to a wide range of scientific themes like: from the
117 measurement of diversity by satellite imagery (Rocchini et al., 2021) to the
118 prediction of spatio-temporal patterns of species assemblages (Guisan & Rah-
119 bek, 2011), from the mapping process of plant strategy types (Schmidtlein
120 et al., 2012) to Bayesian geostatistical modelling of discrete-valued processes
121 (Zheng et al. , 2023).

122 **3 R solutions**

123 To ensure replicability under any software and condition, it is best prac-
124 tice to propose FOSS solutions to the problem at hand. Moreover, FOSS
125 guarantees high reproducibility and robustness, giving the ability to enter
126 the code of a computational process, test it, and potentially improve it.
127 Among the different solutions based on FOSS, R (R Core Team , 2023)
128 represents one of the most widely used software worldwide, providing for
129 both official packages (e.g. the Comprehensive R Archive Network, CRAN,
130 <https://cran.r-project.org/>) and additional packages in external reposi-
131 tories (e.g. GitHub, <https://github.com/>). A complete history of man-
132 agement of colors in R is provided by Zeileis and Murrell (2023).

133 Instead of constraining the user to import and export images and make
134 the rendering in a dedicated internet site, it would be preferable to allow users
135 to see scientific graphs in a proper way under a unique coding workflow. From
136 this point of view, R is the perfect solution due to its wide usage by several
137 users attaining to very different communities.

138 There are different R based solutions for: (i) checking graphs for potential
139 colorblind unfriendliness, (ii) providing colorblind friendly palettes, and (iii)
140 redrawing images using colorblind friendly colors.

141 **3.1 Simulation of colorblindness**

142 It is impossible to fully understand the sensations of someone else (Viénot
143 et al. , 1995). This said, simulations of color vision offer a valuable tool
144 for researchers involved in the creation of scientific graphs to understand the
145 potential use of them, also considering color vision impairments. Packages
146 are devoted to simulating both (i) color palettes and (ii) entire graphs for
147 the different types of colorblindness previously described.

148 In the first case, packages such as `colorspace` (Zeileis et al. , 2020), and
149 built upon it, `colorblindcheck` package (Nowosad , 2019), allow a direct

150 comparison of different color palettes. The `colorblindcheck` package pro-
151 vides the ability to simulate the vision of a color palette and to calculate
152 the distances between colors inside a palette for each type of colorblindness.
153 Here, as an example, we use the R function `rainbow` that generates a rain-
154 bow color palette with a given number of colors. The palette can be checked
155 using the `palette_check` function as follows:

```
156  
157 rainbow_pal <- rainbow(7)  
158 colorblindcheck::palette_check(rainbow_pal, plot=TRUE)
```

159
160 This code will generate the rainbow color palette as it is seen by different
161 color vision impairments (Figure 3) and a summary data frame.

162		name	n	tolerance	ncp	ndcp	min_dist	mean_dist	max_dist
163	1	normal	7	12.13226	21	21	12.132257	61.06471	107.63470
164	2	deuteranopia	7	12.13226	21	19	2.572062	44.29065	85.87461
165	3	protanopia	7	12.13226	21	17	3.647681	47.63882	83.28286
166	4	tritanopia	7	12.13226	21	20	2.025647	47.41585	83.77189

167 The original rainbow palette with seven colors has 21 pairs of colors (`ncp`),
168 with a minimum distance of 12.13, a mean distance of 61.06 and a maximum
169 distance of 107.63 for normal vision. All pairs in the original palette are dif-
170 ferentiable (`ndcp`, the number of pairs of colors with a distance greater than
171 the tolerance level, `n`). The default tolerance is set as the minimum distance
172 between two colors in the original input palette; however, it can be set to
173 a different value. The versions of the palette for the different types of col-
174 orblindness exhibit, in general, lower distances between colors, which means
175 that they are less differentiable. Most importantly, the minimum distances
176 between colors are much lower for the different types of colorblindness, sug-
177 gesting that the colors are less differentiable for people with these conditions.
178 Thus, we can summarise that the original rainbow palette is not suitable for
179 people with color vision impairments.

180 Concerning simulations of entire graphs, the `colorblindr` ([https://](https://github.com/clauswilke/colorblindr)
181 github.com/clauswilke/colorblindr) package allows one to check for prob-
182 lems in rainbow color based graphs. As an example, once the dependency
183 package `ggplot2` has been installed, a default plot can be generated by:

```
184  
185  
186 library(ggplot2)  
187 explot <- ggplot(iris, aes(Sepal.Length, fill=Species)) +  
188 geom_density(alpha=0.7)
```

189
190 Hence, the `cvd_grid()` function would plot how the `explot` graph is seen

Figure 3: Simulation of the vision of a color palette by the different types of colorblindness described in section 1.

191 by colorblind people (Figure 4), with different colorblind related diseases:

192

193 `colorblindr::cvd_grid(explot)`

194

195 3.2 Colorblind friendly color palettes

196 One of the very first attempts to create an open access colorblind friendly
 197 palette was performed by Smith & van der Walt (1995) (see van der Walt
 198 , 2024). Starting from a closed source color palette called "parula" from
 199 *Parula americana* bird, they developed the first version of the viridis color
 200 palette, which, ranging from blue to yellow is a first example of colorblind
 201 friendly gamut. The name, meaning "green" in latin, come out from several
 202 animal species like the snake *Dendroaspis viridis*, the fish *Chromis viridis*
 203 and the bird *Tersina viridis*. The viridis color palette was then implemented
 204 in an R package called `viridis` (Garnier et al., 2023).

205 The palettes developed in the `viridis` package were designed or adjusted
 206 from previous palettes maintaining three basic principles: (i) colorfulness,
 207 covering a broad range of options in order to enhance the visibility of dis-
 208 tinctions; (ii) perceptual uniformity, with values in close proximity exhibiting
 209 similar colors and far values displaying more distinct colors; (iii) robustness
 210 to colorblindness, so that the aforementioned characteristics are valid for
 211 individuals with typical types of color vision impairment.

Figure 4: The `colorblindr` allows users to check for the color friendliness of their graphs simulating the vision of people with different kinds of colorblind impairment. Simulation of the vision of a color palette by the different types of colorblindness described in section 1.

212 Several R tools provide colorblind-friendly color palettes, including built-
213 in functions such as *hcl.colors* and *palette.colors* (R Core Team , 2023; Zeileis
214 and Murrell, 2023). The *RColorBrewer* and *rcartocolor* packages are also
215 popular choices (Neuwirth , 2014; Nowosad et al. , 2018). The previ-
216 ously mentioned *colorblindr* package offers a similar color palette called
217 `scale_color_OkabeIto`, which is comparable to the *cividis* palette of the
218 *viridis* package. Another useful tool is the *cols4all* package, which allows
219 users to check the properties of various color palettes, including colorblind-
220 ness simulation. Finally, the *colorBlindness* package provides a colorblind-
221 ness simulator and offers color palettes specifically designed for colorblind
222 individuals.

223 3.3 Creating graphs with improved color palettes

224 The above described packages provide possibilities to create colorblind friendly
225 palettes. However, they alone are not able to rerender existing graphs. For
226 this reason, the *cblindplot* package has been developed. It is currently
227 available in GitHub at <https://github.com/ducciorocchini/cblindplot>,
228 and also being under evaluation in the Comprehensive R Archive Network
229 (CRAN, <https://cran.r-project.org/>). It allows users to directly input
230 an image and a colorblind disease type, and plots a new image with an im-
231 proved color palette (Rocchini et al. , 2023).

232 The first method developed in *cblindpot* is based on a reduction of the
233 dimensionality of the input image by a Principal Component Analysis (PCA)
234 and a rescaling of the colors on the first PC. For each type of colorblindness
235 disease, an appropriate legend following Viénot et al. (1995) is then ap-
236 plied, based on the *viridis* package. As an example, a person affected by
237 protanopia could make use of the founding function (`cblind.plot()`) as:

238

239

```
240 rainbowinput = "rainbow.png"  
241 cblindpot::cblind.plot(rainbowinput, cvd="protanopia")
```

242

243

244 The above code leads to a colorblind-friendly image like the one reported
245 in Figure 5.

246 This method is straightforward, but (i) it only works for cases where the
247 input color palette is sequential (its luminance changes linearly), and (ii)
248 there is no control on colors of minima and maxima in the output, due to
249 uncontrolled rescaling of the original values by Principal Component Analy-
250 sis.

Figure 5: An image of the Rio Negro (Amazon forest, at Manaus, Brazil), using the ASTER satellite (source: <https://photojournal.jpl.nasa.gov/catalog/PIA26196>). We provide an example considering protanopia. Using the `cblindplot` package the original image, which is poorly visible for color-blind people, is rescaled to a single layer with Principal Component Analysis, and a meaningful color palette is applied.

251 An alternative second method is based on the legend sampling. It re-
 252 quires one more input argument, an image of the original image color legend
 253 (it can be, for example, cropped from the original image using an external
 254 graphic editor, such as GIMP). Legend sampling involves regularly selecting
 255 the colors from the input legend (e.g., from the top to the bottom), and then
 256 replacing the original input colors in the provided main image with colors
 257 from a colorblind friendly palette.

```
258
259 my_image = "my_image.png"
260 my_legend = "my_legend.png"
261 cblindplot::cblind.plot(my_image, legend = my_legend)
262
```

263 Additional methods for legend sampling could be based on a classification
 264 of colors by making use of neural networks (e.g., by the `nnblind()` function):

```
265
266 my_image = rast("my_image.png")
267 nnblind(my_image)
268
```

269 Initially, the neural network categorizes colors in the image into thirteen
 270 classes: white, red, brown, orange, yellow, light green, green, light blue,
 271 blue, pink, violet, grey, and black. Subsequently, the identified colors are
 272 substituted with a colorblind-friendly palette meticulously curated by oph-
 273 thalmologists and orthoptists from Luigi Sacco Hospital (Milan, Italy). This
 274 specialized palette is tailored to the specific colorblind condition, ensuring
 275 an enhanced visual experience for users. Although there is a limited number

Figure 6: A classified map of the Himalaya region with rainbow colors in normal vision, and the colorblind-friendly maps created by the `nncblind()` function for protanopia, deuteranopia and tritanopia.

276 of colors to be classified, this method has proved its efficiency in creating
 277 readable maps for colorblind people, especially when categorical maps are
 278 transformed, as in Figure 6.

279 4 Conclusion

280 The main goal of data visualisation is to make it easier to identify patterns,
 281 trends and outliers in large data sets. The choice of colors can significantly
 282 impact how people interpret and interact with the data. A very good example
 283 is provided by the `ggplot2` R package and its derivatives (see <https://www.cedricscherer.com/2019/08/05/a-ggplot2-tutorial-for-beautiful-plotting-in-r/>
 284 for an impressive and colorful tutorial).

286 Color vision impairment presents a notable obstacle in the visualization
 287 and comprehension of data, especially in the realm of ecology. It is essential
 288 to accurately interpret maps and graphs to understand complex ecological
 289 processes, ranging from the distribution of species to the dynamics of ecosys-
 290 tems. Yet, for individuals with colorblindness, conventional visual displays
 291 can frequently lead to misinterpretation or confusion. This paper highlighted
 292 the importance of developing tools and approaches that take into account the

293 unique needs of individuals with color vision impairments in data visualiza-
294 tion. The suggested R packages offer practical remedies to improve the clarity
295 of maps and graphs intended for people with color vision impairments.

296 While the use of colorblind-friendly palettes is guided by the principle
297 of inclusivity, caution is needed when using multiple palettes within a single
298 visualization. The use of different palettes may lead to color overlap or hue
299 merging, even if they are color-blind friendly. Therefore, it is essential to
300 verify palette compatibility using the packages shown in Box 1 to ensure
301 that colors do not blend across the various layers of a visualization.

302 In mapping contexts, where polygons often delineate political or ecologi-
303 cal boundaries using distinct colors, introducing a second palette to represent
304 an ecological/environmental gradient at several study sites can lead to color
305 overlap for color-blind individuals. Specifically, some points might merge
306 with the background, becoming indistinguishable to those with color vision
307 impairments. In these cases, adopting a grayscale gradient for the back-
308 ground is an effective way to address this problem. Grayscale gradients,
309 which rely on luminance rather than hue, offer a scale of differentiation that
310 is universally discernible, making them useful in complex visualizations re-
311 quiring clear distinctions between different data layers. However, when the
312 visualization includes many classes, even grayscale gradients may lack dis-
313 cernibility for everyone. In such scenarios, the use of different textures can
314 facilitate the necessary distinction.

315 We provided several R examples to face the colorblindness issue during
316 data analysis in streamed pipelines. Additional packages exist to (i) simulate
317 vision deficiencies and to (ii) apply colorblind-friendly palettes. For space and
318 narrative reasons, we decided to include them in Box 1.

319 Moreover, we also encourage publishers to embed a tool in their systems
320 so that someone viewing a graph/image online could literally click a button
321 and change the visualisation, as in many colorblind simulator sites like *Coblis*
322 (<https://www.color-blindness.com/coblis-color-blindness-simulator/>)
323 or *Pilestone* (<https://pilestone.com/pages/color-blindness-simulator-1>).
324 This would represent an enhancement for people to be able to easily change
325 the graph/image into an accessible form.

326 Finally, as ecology continues to evolve, the tools and methodologies used
327 to communicate research findings must keep pace. Adopting a higher aware-
328 ness of the needs of colorblind people represents an important step in fostering
329 inclusivity and accessibility.

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351 **Box 1 - Packages related to colorblindness available in R**

352 **Simulation of colorblindness**

- 353 • `colorspace` contains tools for manipulating and assessing colors, it
354 also has functions for simulating color vision deficiencies (Zeileis et al.
355 , 2020);
- 356 • `colorblindcheck` simulates colorblindness of a given color palette, it
357 also provides numerical summaries of the pairwise distances between
358 colors inside a palette (Nowosad , 2019).
- 359 • `colorblindr` simulates colorblindness for R graphic objects, including
360 `ggplot2` (McWhite et al. , 2023);
- 361 • `colorBlindness` contains palettes for colorblind people and a color
362 vision impairment simulator (Ou, 2021);

363 **Colorblind-friendly color palettes**

- 364 • `RColorBrewer` provides color palettes for R, including colorblind-friendly
365 palettes (Neuwirth , 2014);
- 366 • `viridis` provides color palettes for R, including colorblind-friendly
367 palettes) (Garnier et al., 2023);
- 368 • `rcartocolor` provides color palettes for R, including colorblind-friendly
369 palettes (Nowosad et al. , 2018);
- 370 • `cols4all` provides a selection of color palettes designed to be acces-
371 sible to people with normal color vision and color vision impairments
372 (Tennekes et al. , 2023).

373 **Creating graphs with improved color palettes**

- 374 • `cblindplot` allows to convert any rainbow color graph into a meaning-
375 ful graph for colorblind people just digitising the type of colorblindness
376 (Rocchini et al. , 2023)

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